

D5.2 Success Stories Videos

WP5 – Dissemination and Sustainability

02.09.2019

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Success stories videos, including motivational material that have been developed under the Families_Share project and more specifically under Task 5.2 “Awareness-raising event” of WP5 “Dissemination and Sustainability”.

The success stories videos contain material – recordings from the pilot locations (Citylabs) as well as interviews of parents participating in the pilot activities that have been implemented by the project partners during the first iteration period. They are a collection of good practices, success stories and experiences of CityLab participants – the so-called heroes - in WP3. Three (3) video interviews were expected by each CityLab. More than 3 were received in most of the cases. The videos are shared on Families_Share website and in social media channels aiming to encourage further involvement and activation, especially in the second iteration, of the project.

The success stories – video interviews were edited as promotional material, with the intention to reach a general audience, consisting of both adults and children and seek to raise public awareness about the “services” provided via the project.

Furthermore, the videos are also addressing more specific target audiences, namely public stakeholders and potential replicators, by presenting the potentials of the project as well as citizens’ will to use the application. They aim at encouraging participation and involvement in the activities facilitated and promoted via the Families_Share application translating existing needs to real solutions.

Table of Contents

1	Preamble	7
1.1	Intended audience	7
1.2	Document structure	7
2	Introduction	7
3	Video Interviews – Collection of stories & motivational material from the pilot locations	10
3.1	UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI -	10
3.1.1	Families_Share Bologna CityLab - Experience of parents	11
3.1.2	Families_Share Bologna CityLab Radio Interview	13
3.1.3	Families_Share Bologna CityLab - Our partner Carlotta presenting our project	14
3.2	SMART VENICE SRL -	15
3.2.1	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Anna!	15
3.2.2	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Milena!	17
3.2.3	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Nicolas!	19
3.2.4	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Maria!	20
3.2.5	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Maurizio!	22
3.2.6	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Dream Team!!	23
3.2.7	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Nadia!	25
3.2.8	Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Laura!	27
3.3	FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER FBK Italy -	28
3.3.1	Families_Share Trento CityLab - Friday MiniLab communication campaign	29
3.3.2	Families_Share Trento CityLab - All about the project	29
3.3.3	Families_Share Trento CityLab - Families_Share application	30
3.4	CENTRE FOR SUPPORT AND ADVANCEMENT OF EMPLOYMENT FOR WOMEN IN THESSALONIKI-ERGANI -	31
3.4.1	Families_Share Ergani CityLab - Experience of Sofia!	31
3.5	DE STUYVERIJ, Kortrijk, Belgium -	33
3.5.1	Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Abas!	34
3.5.2	Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Kelly!	35
3.5.3	Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Kiara!	36
3.5.4	Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Mina!	37

3.5.5	Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Tom!	39
3.6	SZULOK HAZA ALAPITVANY, Hungary -	40
3.6.1	Families_Share Budapest CityLab - Experience of Gabriella!	40
4	Conclusions	41
5	Additional Technical Information	42
6	Appendix A - Families_Share Consent form for Photography/Filming	45
7	Appendix B - Guidelines provided to partners prior to the audiovisual recordings.	46

1 Preamble

1.1 Intended audience

This document targets Families_Share consortium members in order to reflect the progress of the implementation of the first release of the Families_Share platform, contributing at the same time to the overall dissemination of the activities and the results of the project.

This document constitutes a report of the audiovisual material collected, edited and developed under WP5 (Dissemination & Sustainability) and Task 5.2 (Awareness raising campaign: online, offline). It can be used as an overview of the success stories videos, and also as a detailed presentation of the value those videos add to the dissemination activities. In addition, the document can be used as a report for the reviewers of the European Commission, as well as a guide - practical tool for Horizon2020 - HorizonEurope dissemination managers of ongoing- future projects, who are willing to explore our successful strategy and capitalize on it. Ending, it could be used by the project's CityLabs and the community managers to support them on the continuation of their local dissemination efforts.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organized as follows:

The first section of this report consists of a preamble, containing the first information one needs when reading this Deliverable Report. Section 2 consists of the introduction to the Task as well as to the objectives, the process, the usage and the messages used in the Success stories videos/promotional videos. Moving on, Section 3 "Video Interviews – Collection of stories & motivational material from the pilot locations" consists of the presentation of all recordings per CityLab accompanied with all the available information. Section 4 concludes the Deliverable, while section 5 provides the reader with information on the technical issues. Finally, Section 6 and 7 are the appendixes containing the guidelines and templates provided to all the members of the consortium during the recording period.

2 Introduction

Objectives: The aim of this deliverable is to raise public awareness on existing needs and the solutions provided by ICT and European projects, on childcare and support the overall targets relating to behavioural change, a focal point of our project. The videos will be used as a means of reaching out to the general public, in order to inform it about the opportunities of the Families_Share project, and engage public/private stakeholders, organisations and

parents/families in supporting/replicating/joining the European growing family of Families_Share.

The use of success stories – interviews/ promotional videos with a focused and concise script, containing powerful messages about needs related to childcare, limited time and limited funding and all pertinent information about the project in an engaging way, is expected to serve the above-mentioned objectives.

Process: The list of the 18 stories, three for each of the project's citylabs and the concept for each video were finalized by project partners in the period of the first pilot implementation, M15 until M21 of the project. ViLabs and Ergani subsequently held final deliberations with production companies, which have been identified as suitable sub-contractors, evaluated their proposals on the project's final number of videos, and resulted to the selection of the current production company professionals.

It has been decided by project partners that all videos will be accompanied by English subtitles. Although not expected/ foreseen within the project's Description of Action, Translation in the rest project languages will also be provided on a later stage. Each pilot partner will take care of the translation & voice-over (where this is needed) in their respective languages.

The videos were grouped with a view of having a balanced set of videos for the initial roll-out of the platform, comprising both awareness-raising / educational videos and videos presenting the opportunities of Families_Share.

According to Task 5.2, each CityLab was to provide with 3 interviews/audiovisual material, supporting the promotional activities of the project, **18** in total as the CityLabs are currently 6. So far, **21** interviews/promotional material have been shared to the Project's YouTube channel, reaching and surpassing the initial KPI, while additional videos are expected soon. Of course, due to privacy issues, there have been cases where parents were not that willing to be recorded (example of the Thessaloniki and Trento CityLab). However, the content received from the rest pilot partners was enough to cover the missing two videos. Moreover, graphic videos containing key messages and information about the project and the application have also been used (case of Trento CityLab). Interviews will be continued during the second pilot implementation in order to maximize the dissemination and reach as many individuals as possible.

Use and Dissemination: The videos will be accessible to all visitors (anonymous users), through the project’s website and social media accounts, as well as the website and social media channels of project partners.

Moreover, pilot partners will integrate the videos also in their individual dissemination and communication activities. In pursuing their efforts to attract and engage new users/parents/families, they will use the videos in their contacts with potential users/adopters.

Regarding external exploitation, the video material developed will be made available to organisations who wish to disseminate it to promote ideas, narratives, needs and possible solutions.

Key messages: The choices made in relation to the content, information and design of these informative and motivational videos are intended to serve the objective of clearly and effectively communicating high impact messages able to affect and engage a broad audience. While each video is tailored to the priority and defined the target audience, there are some key messages recurring throughout the video material, since viewers are not necessarily expected to watch many/all videos.

The concept of these messages has emerged from WP1 and Deliverable D1.1 as well as from WP3 and the implementation of the pilot activities. The videos/interviews translate the identified obstacles, barriers as well as realities and the identified perceptions of local stakeholders into creative communication material, and include:

CityLabs – Concepts – Promotional Interviews/content	
Bologna CityLab	Childcare needs and work/life balance, Informal support, Other forms of informal but paid support for managing childcare, sharing care with other parents, focus on time-sharing, Time-banking, Security and trust, Role of technologies in managing childcare and such.
Kortrijk De Stuyverij CityLab	
Thessaloniki CityLab	
Trento CityLab	
Venezia CityLab	
Gyor CityLab	

3 Video Interviews – Collection of stories & motivational material from the pilot locations

3.1 UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI -

The very active CityLab of Bologna, Italy has proceeded to a great number of dissemination activities during the first pilot implementation period. Among these was also the conduction of several interviews with parents and families participating in the piloting activities and sharing their opinion and support towards the Families_Share project, application and narrative in general. Interviews were taken, following the rules and directions of the corresponding task, from parents, most of them of the male gender.

In addition, the representative of the CityLab of Bologna gave an interview to a famous bologna radio show ([Radio 1088's Show](#)) introducing the project and reaching a great amount of radio audience. The recording has been transformed into a video format in order to reach an additional audience and support the dissemination activities of the project.

Moreover, a presentation supported by social media live streaming took place in Abruzzo and with the support of the **Biblio Attack** and the library of Giampaolo, that has been hosting the event. A recording of the event is available on the Families_Share social media, while a reproduction of the interview given to the local tv station "LAQTV Abruzzo" is available of the Families_Share YouTube channel as well as in this Deliverable report.

In total, three video recordings have been shared on the project's YouTube channel, more than six in the project social media accounts and more than 6 fathers have recorded their support to the project.

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the interview, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual interview.

All interviews have been recorded in the CityLabs national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming period.

3.1.1 Families_Share Bologna CityLab - Experience of parents

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, parents (fathers) and families.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the Italian and English minutes of the Interview with the Bolognian parents.

CARLOTTA (Bologna CityLab of Families_Share project)

IT: E' un progetto che rientra all'interno del programma Horizon 2020 dell'Unione Europea, in cui ci sono tre città in Italia Trento, Venezia, Bologna, che cerca di innovare e quindi utilizzare gli strumenti tecnologici per aiutare nella vita quotidiana la gestione della vita familiare da parte dei genitori nell'organizzazione del tempo libero dei bambini e nell'organizzazione del loro tempo libero e di lavoro.

EN: This is a project included in the Horizon 2020 program of the European Union, in which three Italian cities are involved Trento, Venice, Bologna. It seeks to innovate social issues and to use technological tools in order to help the day-to-day management of family life on the part of parents, in organizing children's free time and their leisure and work time.

ROCCO (Liliana and Cecilia's father)

IT: Penso che sia un progetto interessante perché c'è bisogno di aiutarsi reciprocamente

EN: I think it is an interesting project because we need to help each other.

ROBERTO (Andrea's father)

IT: Credo che il Families Share sia un progetto bellissimo perché intercetta il bisogno di tutte le famiglie compresa la mia che è quella di poter condividere l'esperienza che facciamo tutti i giorni con i nostri bambini

EN: I think that Families Share is a beautiful project because it merges the need of all families including mine, that is to be able to share the experience we have every day with our children

EMMANUELE (Paolo and Chiara's father)

IT: mi sembra di tornare alle mie origini, io vengo dalla provincia, vengo da Riccione, invece è molto difficile in città riuscire ad approfondire rapporti con i vicini o con quelli della tua zona

EN: It is like going back to my origins. I come from the countryside. I come from Riccione. On the contrary, it is very difficult in a town environment to be able to deepen relations with neighbours or people of your area.

MATTEO (Giosuè and Natalia's father)

IT: Dove andare a lavorare? Dal mio punto di vista servirebbe qualcosa di più delle piattaforme già esistenti, quel qualcosa di più potrebbe essere dato da un rinforzo sulla sicurezza, perché come sappiamo le altre piattaforme sono social media e quindi aperte a tutto il pubblico, invece dare un valore aggiunto, un servizio di nicchia, un servizio che possa realmente incidere e dare un supporto reale alle famiglie.

EN: From my point of view, to have something more than the existing platforms would be useful, and that one thing could be given by a reinforcement on security issues, because as we know the other platforms are social media and for this reason they are open to the whole public, instead of giving an added value, a nice service, a service that can really affect and give real support to families.

LORENZO (Camilla's father)

IT: La cosa che mi lascia perplesso potrebbe essere la sicurezza legata agli altri genitori che se sono tanti dovrebbero essere conosciuti o dovrebbe esserci una garanzia di feedback. In realtà i servizi potrebbero essere tanti, i favori da passarsi potrebbero essere molteplici. Da andare a prendere a scuola o qualche incombenza domestica come l'aiuto per la spesa, Però l'idea è intelligente e molto ben pensata.

EN: The perplexing issue for me might be the security related to the other parents. If there are many parents, they should all be known, or there should be a guarantee of feedback. Actually, several services could be provided; the favours to be made could be multiple. From going to school or some home business like shopping aid, but the idea is smart and very well thought out.

GIUSEPPE (Lavinia's father)

IT: Sicuramente è un'idea che spacca, quindi bene.

EN: It is definitely an idea that rocks, so well done.

3.1.2 Families_Share Bologna CityLab Radio Interview

Radio interview at local radio, "Fuoricabina, Leila's Birthday Live from Belmeloro", presenting Families_Share project and the partnership with Leila association. The local radio is managed by university students in Bologna.

The graphic features the Families Share logo on the left, with the text "Radio Interview" below it. Contact information for the Bologna CityLab is provided, including an email address (bolognat@families-share.eu), a website (www.families-share.eu), and a Facebook link. On the right, there is a photo of Carlotta Berionni, the Community Manager, and a logo for "RADIO 1088'S SHOW" with a radio frequency icon.

Per informazione sul progetto CITY LAB di BOLOGNA:
 bolognat@families-share.eu
 www.families-share.eu
 Families Share Italian CityLabs

Carlotta Berionni
 Families-Share Bologna
 Community Manager

RADIO 1088'S SHOW

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 CAPS
 Topic: ICT-11-2017, Type of action: IA, Grant agreement No 780783

CAPSS Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability & Social Innovation

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant initiatives.

3.1.3 Families_Share Bologna CityLab - Our partner Carlotta presenting our project

Thanks to Biblio attack, a self-organized group whose members share the reading passion with their children, Families_Share has been invited in Abruzzo. They are interested in importing Families_Share project and app in Pescara, and this was the very first meeting with the consortium.

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant initiatives.

3.2 SMART VENICE SRL -

The Venice CityLab has provided with hours of recordings and more than eight (8) long (10-15 minutes) interviews from parents, who have participated in the two pilot activities that took place in Cannaregio and Marghera (more information can be found in D3.2). Both pilot activities have been covered by professionals who have recorded the whole events. The long recordings of the events have been cut and edited in order to result in the seven available interviews. Additional footage and interviews will be used in the future as additional promotional material for social media use as well as for other dissemination activities.

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the interview, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual interview. All interviews have been recorded in the CityLabs national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming months.

3.2.1 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Ana!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Ana.

Ana, why have you decided to participate in Families Share?

We have decided to participate in this project because, like many other families here, we don't have any extra help for our daughter's care.

Because we don't have grandparents, uncles and aunts, siblings, or cousins here, we liked the possibility to receive support from a 'family-based' structure rather than from a school or from a professional childcare service.

Which is, in your opinion, the added value of this family-based idea, conversely to a professional service?

It is exactly its family dimension because you entrust other parents with the care of your child and vice-versa.

The great thing is that you know other families with whom you create a network of mutual help and new friendships, both between parents and children.

It is not by payment, and this is also an added value since none has an economic interest. It is a complete different childcare idea.

You already did your shift as a voluntary parent in childcare during this summer camp. How was the experience of taking care of other children together with yours?

This, for me, is the surprising part. I have only one daughter, and I was not used to taking care of a group of children

Taking care of more children of different ages, is really a new and very stimulating experience, that allows you to take out your unknown resources.

To adapt your program to all these children of different ages, both females and males, it was not easy, but it was fun. After a while, it becomes easier and easier. For me, it was really stimulating!

Were you worried at the beginning?

Yes of course, but I think it's quite normal because, the one who has a lot of children and his own family network of support do not have these needs. Instead, we are not used either to take care of a group of children or to entrust others with the care of our daughter.

However, it was a really positive surprise for us

So, Ana, you were saying that for you, the Families share project was a positive experience, what about your daughter?

This was also surprising, because we, as parents, had some doubts in the beginning. For her was different, she is normally very calm, but when we brought her here, she changed, she was enthusiastic. It was a surprise!

We expected more boredom and scepticism also from the children's side, wondering who all these adults are, given that they didn't know us... No, it was everything alright.

Of course, when there is his/her own parent, the child changes a bit, and he/she becomes a little less manageable, but it is normal, they are little, my daughter is just 4.

Has there been a problem for her to change the parent of reference every day? This was pointed out as a possible criticality

We didn't know how she would have reacted. But all these children frequently do so at least at the nursery school. Thus, they are used to change often point of reference.

Every morning I was telling her "Today you have to listen to these parents», and she was ok with this, she was adapting immediately.

Because they are used to do so and for some aspects, they are older than what we think!

3.2.2 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Milena!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Milena.

Milena, why have you decided to participate in this experience?

Hi, I have decided to participate in this project because of its fair modalities, in which parents take the role of taking care of children of other families.

I like the cooperation and collaboration between parents who give a good example to children. Also, in this way, it is possible to help families that cannot afford to pay a summer camp that lasts the whole summer, or those families where both parents work

We help each other, and this is a good example for our children!

How is this experience going? How did this morning lab go?

I think very well, but also the one of yesterday of which I saw the pictures and videos!

Everyone proposed an activity in accordance with his/her own passions and personality, like the clay laboratory and the one of Bangladeshi dance.

Also, this fact that there are different ethnicities is very beautiful, so that everyone proposes an activity of his/her own culture. This morning everything went well, children gladly participated in the yoga for children, which I proposed them.

It is enjoyable. I think it is going really well!

Would you recommend this experience to other parents?

Yes, definitely, it is very beautiful. In my opinion, it is a positive example also for our society, because we have forgotten this aspect of being well together, of creating a mutual-help community, that we do not have to grow just individually, together we grow better!

3.2.3 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Nicolas!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Nicola.

Nicola, why have you decided to participate in this experience?

It is for sure something interesting because parents are directly involved, so you have the possibility to know other people, other families and children who live in your own neighbourhood. So, we decided to try this experiment!

How is it going until now?

It is going pretty well. My son found himself quite well; he is playing and interacting with everyone. We are satisfied!

Children received different inputs, besides the simple tasks of painting and playing, they have sung and learnt Bangladeshi dances. Thus, there are new activities that they are enjoying!

Therefore, they have enjoyed the laboratories, right?

Yes, they liked them!

Would you recommend this experience to other parents?

Yes, of course. It is an enjoyable experience.

Thus, do you see a follow up to this experience?

Yes, yes, of course, it is doable, maybe with wider planning. Indeed, as I said before, I was invited by another parent, and I did not manage to get in contact earlier with this project. However, by spreading this initiative earlier, I am sure there would have been a bigger participation!

3.2.4 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Maria!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found here.

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Maria.

Maria, as a parent, how are you experiencing this Families Share summer week?

Families Share is a nice project because as a parent it asks you to show your creativity and to take out all your desire to play!

It makes you a child again, but at the same time it asks you to be responsible for a group of 5-6 children and to create activities for children together with other parents that maybe you don't know so well.

The beautiful aspect of the project lays exactly in the trust that you need to bring out and rediscover.

Trust in your capabilities of empathy and creativity, but also trust in other adults, that allows you to create something beautiful, to build a network and a community

How are your children experiencing this project?

Initially, with some doubts, asking themselves how this experience will be, with parents as entertainers, they were a bit perplexed.

Nevertheless, since the first day, they were really happy, and they have come to play every day very gladly.

My main doubt at the beginning was that they were not ready to meet every day new people as entertainers.

However, this fear has proved to be quite unfounded because probably children are much more open than adults.

So, in the end, everything was alright. My children had high expectations about my performance as an entertainer... They wanted to make a good impression.

In the end, I think I have satisfied them.

How is this experience going, from a community manager's perspective?

Very well. We thought this project as an opportunity to give it to the families.

Both to create networks, communities and reactivate social and neighbourhood bounds, and to find a possible solution to common problems of work-life balance.

The needs assessment that we did was correct, and it corresponded to what families are looking for.

Moreover, we are also working to overcome a basic mistrust imposed by an objective climate of fear and diffidence that is present in our society.

We tend a bit to withdraw from others, to think about our own, and to nurture a bit of distrust towards each other.

But we are influenced by this only partially. As soon as we open to concrete experiences that inspires us to create something together with others, something beautiful and creative, this diffidence falls down very easily and quickly!

3.2.5 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Maurizio!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Maurizio.

Maurizio, why have you decided to participate in the Families Share project?

Because I liked it, I found the project nice, funny and useful. It is an experience that I still have to do completely, but it seems that is going really well.

Children are enjoying it and the same stands for the parents, it seems to be a beautiful way to be all together!

What does your son think about these summer activities of Families Share?

I don't know, I still have to know what he thinks about them [the son is answering] "I like them!"

[Maurizio is asking his son] Why do you like them?

Do you like them because you are throwing me water? [Davide] "yes."

And what else? Are there nice children? [Davide] "yes."

What about the entertainers? Are they nice? [Davide] "yes a lot."

And you played a lot, right? A lot of drawings, collages, games...

And what did you do now? Water games?

Maurizio, what are you planning for the activity of tomorrow?

We are going to create a huge board game; we will draw it and then paint it!

Did you have some doubts about your decision to cover the role of voluntary parents and to take care of a group of children?

No, I didn't. My partner invited me to join, and this assured me. Then, I saw that I am in a group of trustful people!

When I was younger, I was a basketball coach, thus I have always played with children!

Being together with other adults makes me more confident. Being alone with a group of children it's always more difficult!

3.2.6 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Dream Team!!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with our friends Zoe, Bibek and Nesta!

So, Zoe, are you happy to participate in Families Share this week?

Yes!

Do you like it till now?

Yes, it is pleasant!

Which activity did you enjoy most so far?

Until now, I enjoyed a lot the clay laboratory that we did yesterday.

How do you see your mum as a 'teacher' in this experience?

Mmm, she is good!

Yes, she is very good, although she is used to, she is very good!

Have you made new friends during this experience?

Yes, I made new friends with the other children coming here. I already knew some of them, while the others are now new friends!

That's great! Have you learnt something new?

Beh, yes, some things were new

Like the clay lab?

No for that it was not the first time that I did it, but I have learnt some new words in different languages with Nicola

Would you invite other friends to participate in Families Share?

Yes!

Bibek (on the left) and Nesta (on the right), are you happy to participate in Families Share this week?

Yes!

Which activity did you like most so far?

[Nesta] All [Bibek] All of them

All? don't you have a favourite one?

[Bibek] no, all of them

Did you like today's yoga lab?

[both] yes

How do you see your parents as 'teachers' in this experience?

[Nesta] Good [Bibek] Bad... No, I mean, good

Your mums were very good these days, right?

yes

Have you made new friends during this experience?

yes

Did you know each other before?

No, we didn't

So, you became new friends!

yes

That's great! Have you learnt something new during this experience? What?

[Bibek says something not understandable!!!]

[Nesta] Friendship!

Wow, this is nice. Would you invite other friends to participate in this experience, next year maybe?

[Bibek] ok [Nesta] this year I have invited everyone, but they answered no

ok but maybe next year they will participate

[Nesta] yes it could be

Tell me one thing that you like about these two days

[Bibek] mmm, the yoga activity

wow, beautiful. And you?

[Nesta] the yoga activity as well

3.2.7 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Nadia!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Nadia.

Nadia, why have you decided to participate in Families Share?

Because it is an opportunity for us and for children to be together and to share playtime in an alternative way!

You already did your shift as a voluntary parent in childcare during this summer camp. How was the experience of taking care of other children together with yours?

It is a continuation of what I already do as a teacher, although with a different children age-range, it is an ulterior simplification of playful or didactic moments.

It is nothing completely new even though it is anyway a continuous discovery because children are different!

You also involved your daughter's dad in this experience...

Yes, because we both immediately liked this idea and we think it as teamwork. We right away recognized that the family is the focus of this project

This collaboration seems to us the most natural thing, this sense of community, it should be shared with other families as well.

And how is the experience turning out for your daughter?

Surely positive, she is very enthusiastic and peaceful, she wants to come back every morning: "what are we going to do today?" it is her first thought in the morning

And how is the fact that there are children of different ages?

I think it is a positive thing because the younger children learn from the older and vice versa, and there is a continuous exchange. I think this experience is normal at the end.

It is possible to share the same experience because in every case someone has something to teach.

Families Share, thank you for this opportunity, and we hope to continue with this experience in the future... Thanks!

3.2.8 Families_Share Venice CityLab - Experience of Laura!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Laura.

Laura, why have you decided to participate in this experience?

I have decided to participate because I was looking for an alternative to a traditional summer camp, where parents could share their own skills and make them available to children. I was looking for something different

How is it going until now?

Well, I have tried the yoga lab, and I like it a lot, children responded very well, it is something uncommon for a summer camp, I think it is going really well.

Ans is your child happy?

My child has some little resistances because she is very small, she needs to know the new children and the new environment first, but slowly she is letting herself go.

Would you recommend this experience to other parents?

I would suggest it compatibly with their time/obligations. I want to underline that this experience requires some effort due to its alternative character.

But I am sure it brings also to important results, as every initiative with a certain substance does.

3.3 FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER FBK Italy -

The logo for Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) consists of a stylized blue 'FBK' monogram. Below the monogram, the words 'FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER' are written in a smaller, blue, uppercase, sans-serif font.

The Trento CityLab provided only with one recording of their events. However, two additional informative promotional materials have been developed to support the CityLabs activities. In addition, given the existence of many Italian interviews and promotional material from the rest CityLabs the Trento needs are fully covered. However, interviews will be conducted to families in Trento and shared along with the rest during the second implementation period of the pilot activities.

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the promotional material, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual recording.

All interviews/promotional material have/has been recorded in the CityLab's national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming months. In addition to the promotional material shared the period relevant to this deliverable, a set of audiovisual material, interviews as well as graphic videos will be developed and shared also the upcoming period, both to the YouTube channel and the official social media of the project as well as to the project website.

3.3.1 Families_Share Trento CityLab - Friday MiniLab communication campaign

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, initiatives and companies.

3.3.2 Families_Share Trento CityLab - All about the project

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

The promotional material has been translated into English. Below one can find the English version of the text.

To what extent can time-sharing and informal support be a resource for parents to manage childcare? What role can companies play? How can technology facilitate such collaborative approaches?

Thanks to the synergy between the organizations that are part of **the Trento Family Audit District** and the European **Families_Share** project, we will experiment with a new collaborative approach to improve corporate welfare, through the mobilization and sharing of resources within the company and between companies, with the direct involvement of workers and workers.

Cooperation: We promote the creation of communities that help make everyday life easier, allowing you to find the right balance between work and private life, and create relationships of solidarity and trust in the workplace.

Fun and learning: Parents take turns organizing recreational activities for their children. In this way, children, having fun can participate in the working world of parents and parents can get involved by promoting activities related to their professional role or simply recreational.

Digital innovation: The Families_Share application makes it easier to manage activities and coordinate in order to cover certain time periods and maintain a well-organized shared calendar.

3.3.3 Families_Share Trento CityLab - Families_Share application

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, initiatives and companies.

The promotional material has been translated into English. Below one can find the English version of the text.

THE APPLICATION OF FAMILIES SHARE

The Families_Share app is designed to allow parents and volunteers to coordinate activities and manage shifts between volunteers in an intuitive and fast way.

The intent of the project is to create communities, starting from already existing networks, of people who help themselves in managing their children by creating solidarity relationships and bonds based on trust. Face to face relationships, therefore, remains of fundamental importance.

This is why the app does not want to replace them, but only to support coordination activities and shift management. The app allows users to create groups, manage a shared calendar and create turn-based activities.

These features are designed to support groups of parents working together to co-organize childcare activities. Description of all steps towards the first pilot implementation.

3.4 CENTRE FOR SUPPORT AND ADVANCEMENT OF EMPLOYMENT FOR WOMEN IN THESSALONIKI-ERGANI -

3.4.1 Families_Share Ergani CityLab - Experience of Sofia!

The Thessaloniki CityLab provided with an interview of a single parent, who has taken part to the pilot activities and is already part of an emerging community, eager to not only use the platform but to also start up a new digital social community of parents in need. Additional interviews will be conducted during the second implementation period of the pilot activities.

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the interview, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual interview.

All interviews have been recorded in the CityLabs national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming months.

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens, families and relevant existing and future initiatives.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Sofia.

Today, being a parent is more difficult than ever. We need to be in many places at the same time, combining our work, our family and our personal needs.

In the last decade, the balance between our professional and family lives has been lost. The economic crisis has affected communities throughout Europe and radically changed the opportunities that each family can offer its children.

Reduced social welfare funding and limited childcare services are particularly burdensome for families with young children. Letting the kids on TV or gaming platforms when we can't be with them is a solution?

The struggle is real and daily.

Seven different organizations, universities, businesses and research centres, including the Ergani Center, along with 6 parent communities in Flanders, Bologna, Trento, Venice, Gyor and Thessaloniki, are joining forces to create one innovative and participatory solution:

The Families-share project. Funded by the European Union, combines different factors and approaches where parents and children design activities based on their own real and daily needs. Through this project, families become members of a European movement, create small, trusted communities of friends, partners and neighbours, in which they actively share support for their children, and co-create care, education and recreation solutions, facilitating their daily lives.

The Ergani Center has undertaken the implementation of the project in Thessaloniki, and we are testing our strengths in practice. We suggest local solutions to local problems. Join us to design new activities and become a member of our local lab.

Learn more about the Families_Share project and the Ergani Center

3.5 DE STUYVERIJ, Kortrijk, Belgium -

The De Stuyverij CityLab provided us with five (5) (1- 3 minutes) targeted interviews from parents and children, who have participated in the CityLab's pilot activities (additional information can be found in D3.2). The footage was very interesting and inspiring. Parents were willing to be recorded in order to support the Families_Share project and the Families_Share application. Parents were also recorded holding a banner stating that they are part of the family **"I'm part of the family"**. The latter parts were edited in a single video and have been added as the cover video of the official Families_Share [Facebook page](#).

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the interview, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual interview. All interviews have been recorded in the CityLabs national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming months.

3.5.1 Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Abas!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

My name is Abas
Great, fantastic group!
All the children are nice to play with, and it's great to take your children home happy after a great day playing here.
It's nice when we get to go home, and the children are happy, and there were no accidents
The children find the childcare nice, and they like the other children, it's a good thing if the friends know each other and they listen.
I found this form of childcare through the group "vakantiewerking Groei!", my girlfriend asked me to join, and I said o.k. This is my first time. I will for sure do it again, I saw the positive sides, and it was fun, it is the first time, but it's nice.
Today is really the first day; I feel good to play with the children, it's nice.

3.5.2 Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Kelly!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

My name is Kelly!

We are “the bijspeeltuin IEPER”, we are connected to the tierlantuin, a freinetschool in Ieper, and we are basically a group of parents who organize childcare together.

We chose this form of childcare because I have children and they function better in a small group instead of going to big camps; they are still very young. That was the starting point, by now I realized that it’s the perfect way to meet other parents, to get to know the other children from the school. So, this is the best solution for my whole family.

The biggest advantages for me are that I can drop my kids off with peace of mind, without any big drama’s like when I had to bring them to regular solutions. I get to meet new parents and organize something together. We all pitch in, and we see that other activity planning goes smoother, that we say hi when we meet each other in the hallway. That kind of stuff, there are a lot of advantages.

For my children:

It’s a small group and thus a trusted environment, with parents who know better than the caretakers what is fun for them. They get to play with their friends all day and not with children they don’t know, my children need some time to adapt sometimes in new groups.

My best memories, I have a few

I remember a lot of really great starting moments and end bbq's with the parents; we organise them at the school so we all get together and you really get the time to talk to each other

I also remember a lot of cool games, dress up games, theatre moments, we already did so many things. Also, very cool combinations of parents that create surprising mixes of styles, it creates nice surprises.

The days when the fathers come are very loved, we put them together a lot of the times and that are days where the playing is a lot wilder, and swings get to build, that sort of stuff.

I already have a lot of memories and a lot of pictures from all our summers so yes, I have too many to choose from!

3.5.3 Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Kiara!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

My name is Kiara!

I get to play here with the other children, and that's very fun because we really get to do everything we want. We get to the bike, we can draw with chalk, and we organize little competition games while biking, and that's really fun to do.

The moms looking after us and sometimes dad too, and that is really fun because there are children here that know them.

We make arrangements with the other mothers and that's just fun because my mother is here and my father and then you get to see them, it's just fun like that.

There is a baby here, and I love babies, I get to play with him the whole time, and I really enjoy that.

Most of the time when my mother is here we play with chalk because my mother loves to do that and I really enjoy to make drawings with here.

When my father comes, he mainly just watches the children, and then we bike a lot.

I made new friends and also got to know new mothers I really like, and it's nice because you get to know new people.

I find this way of co-playing more fun because I have a friend here and we get to the bike; you get to do whatever you like. This is just really nice, we have a sandbox we get to play in, and when the weather is good, we play a lot of games. I enjoy this very much.

3.5.4 Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Mina!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

Hello, my name is Mina!

We are the co-playing group: vakantiewerking Groei! we are a group from Vlamertinge; all the kids go to this school. Well, really great group, really great children, really great mothers. All different ages, Yes, really great group!

We searched for a long time to find a suited form of childcare and looked at all the options but you know it's nice for the children, if they can be taking care of in a group where they know all the children, for us also that we know the mothers and that we know who will be providing the care for our children. It's also just a very fun group that organizes nice activities/Creativities for the children, so this was the best option. The hours are very convenient, and the group talks easily to make the arrangements. It's actually a growing friendship in this whole process.

The advantages for me are, the contact with the other mothers. It's something I didn't think of but did emerge the longer I took part. Also, to hear from other mothers that it's not that easy in every household, that it's not all as dreamy all the time, to hear real mothers, that really strengthens each other. So personally, for me that helped me a lot, I also thought I was not made to take care of a large group of children, but I'm really doing well, and it helped boost my self-confidence a lot.

For my son, it's a dream childcare solution. He is counting the days until he can come to the co-playing activities, the mommy day-care as he calls it. At night he returns completely satisfied, he plays with his friends, he knows it, knows the school, so for him it's a unique experience. In the morning he's beside my bed: can I go to the childcare place now!!!

There are a lot of them. For me personally, it's when I put my son to bed and he says: mom, I'm so happy that I can go to the activities here, that really melts the heart. Or you see how satisfied he's chilling on the sofa, still trying to eat a little bit but falling half to sleep, because of all the playing, with the biggest smile on his face. To drop him off, he doesn't even look back, just runs inside, he's happy, that says it all, and I can see it with the other children as well.

We compared a lot of different childcare options, and this was the best option. This place, all the children know each other from school, you know who's taking care of your children. The mothers do it very well; the hours are convenient. We make good agreements with each other; we organize a lot of activities here as well as outside activities, we go to other places, it was the solution that felt good for me, that I could trust, so yes... that's why.

3.5.5 Families_Share De Stuyverij CityLab - Experience of Tom!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

My name is Tom, father of Vic in the “tierlantuin”

Our group exists out of 12 to 15 children, and we come together to play for a whole day.

I find this form of co-playing very nice because you get to know the parents and the children and your own children are taking care of in a familiar environment. That is very nice, and it's great to be able to do it myself.

The biggest advantage is that my child feels at ease together with his friends from his school, not in a group of strangers, that's a real plus for us.

The best moments are the ones where there is sun, and we can sit outside, eat outside, play outside, that's always good.

We are here with a lot of fathers co-playing, almost as many fathers as mothers, it's always fun, playing soccer together when we have good weather, always great!

3.6 SZULOK HAZA ALAPITVANY, Hungary -

The Győr CityLab has provided us with an interview of one parent as well as with photos and some recordings of co-playing activities. The key obstacle here was the parents didn't want to be video recorded. Additional interviews will be conducted during the second implementation period of the pilot activities.

Below one can find snapshots of the online available content, the title of the interview, the link to the Project official YouTube channel as well as the link for each individual interview. All interviews have been recorded in the CityLabs national language. An English translation is available for all interviews, while partners will provide also translations to the rest national languages during the upcoming months.

3.6.1 Families_Share Budapest CityLab - Experience of Gabriella!

The video is available on our [YouTube Channel](#) and can be found [here](#).

Target audience: (active) citizens and families.

The interview has been translated into English. Below one can find the English minutes of the Interview with Gabriella.

Hi, I am Gabriella Vincze, and I'm living in Győr.

I think that nowadays the composition of families has changed a lot and the children usually live far away from their grandparents. I was born in Budapest and my father still lives in Budapest. My mother-in-law and my father-in-law are still active and live here in Győr, but there are no such people living around us who could support us in taking care after our children. At the very most our friends or a babysitter could do that, but you have to pay for babysitting and, as for friends, some of them undertake to spend time with our children but most of them rather not. So, I think that it is a very useful initiative from this aspect since it gives you an additional opportunity in finding help relating childcare.

I think everybody can use this platform for what they want or need to. Those who need help with babysitting or parental supervision can find a new way of finding a solution through this platform. Most of the parents are working during the summer holidays, so it can be a useful tool for sharing childcare-related tasks in this period. It also can be used for organizing the transportation of children to or from kindergarten, or to meet other parents whose children are attending at the same school or kindergarten. In the 21st century, it is not easy to find new connections and new people with similar interests, so it is a very useful tool for organizing programs together and meet other parents and families with who we spend time with pleasure. It is very important that if children are on the same wavelength with each other, as well as mothers and fathers, finally it can help us to find a small community in which we find love and support.

I would gladly use the application.

I would absolutely recommend this to my friends.

"I support Families_Share. I embrace the community. Let's become a Family."

4 Conclusions

The Families_Share awareness-raising campaigns are an important tool towards the project's dissemination and the enlargement of the project's communities. The collected/developed interviews and promotional material of the first pilot implementation as well as the content that will be developed during the second and final period will be shared on the Website(s) and Social Media channels in order to further encourage the active involvement of individuals, citizens, initiatives and organizations. The 21 developed videos will play a key role to the support of all WP5 Dissemination and Sustainability tasks.

5 Additional Technical Information

All videos have been recorded under the guidelines provided by the WP and Task leader and by the subcontracted agency.

The videos have been recorded by the pilot organizations – CityLabs during their pilot activities.

All videos are subtitled in English, following the general rule of the EU projects and in order to maximize the dissemination reach. Moreover, all partners have been asked to provide subtitles for all videos in their national languages. This way, the recordings (interviews and promotional material) will be used in the upcoming period in order to support the dissemination activities as well as the activities relevant to Task 5.3 “Exploitation and Replication Plan” as well as Task 5.4 “Policy Recommendations”.

video number	minutes	Dialogue translation
3X7A8256	00:00:10-00:00:14	Ana, why have you decided to participate in Families Share?
	00:00:15-00:00:26	We have decided to participate in this project because, like many other families here, we don't have any extra help for our daughter's care
	00:00:26-00:00:30	Because we don't have grandparents, uncles and aunts, siblings, or cousins here
	00:00:31-00:00:40	We liked the possibility to receive support from a family-based structure
	00:00:41-00:00:50	rather than from a school or from a professional childcare service. This was the starting idea
	00:00:51-00:00:58	Which is, in your opinion, the added value of this family-based idea, conversely to a professional service?
	00:00:59-00:01:05	It is exactly its family dimension because you entrust other parents with the care of your child and vice-versa
	00:01:06-00:01:17	The great thing is that you know other families with whom you create a network of mutual help and new friendships, both between parents and children.
	00:01:20-00:01:34	It is not by payment and this is also an added value since none has an economic interest. It is a complete different childcare idea.
	00:01:34-00:01:52	You already did your shift as a voluntary parent in childcare during this summer camp. How was the experience of taking care of other children together with yours?
	00:01:52-00:02:01	This for me is the surprising part. I have only one daughter and I was not used to taking care of a group of children
	00:02:02-00:02:13	Taking care of more children of different ages it is really a new and very stimulating experience, that allows you to take out your unknown resources
	00:02:14-00:02:28	To adapt your program to all these children of different ages, both females and males, it was not easy, but it was funny. Then it becomes easier and easier. For me, it was really stimulating
	00:02:28-00:02:33	Were you worried at the beginning?
	00:02:34-00:02:49	Yes of course, but I think it's quite normal because who has a lot of children and the own family network of support do not have these needs. Instead, we are not used either to take care of a group of children or to entrust others with the care of our daughter.
	00:02:50-00:02:56	However, it was a really positive surprise for us
3X7A8257	00:00:02-00:00:13	So, Ana, you were saying that for you the Families Share project was a positive experience, what about your daughter?
	00:00:14-00:00:36	This was also surprising, because we, as parents, had some doubts before to start. For her was different, she is normally very calm, but when we brought her here she changed, she was enthusiastic. It was a surprise
	00:00:37-00:00:45	We expected more boredom and scepticism also from children's side, wondering who all these adults are, given that they didn't know us... No, it was everything alright.

All the recordings have been uploaded to the Families_Share YouTube channel and are publicly available.

In order to protect the Families_Share brand, the Personal information as well as the quality of the YouTube Channel, the comment section has been de-activated.

In addition, in order to maximise the audience and the highest possible reach, a series of targeted tags have been added to each and every video. *“According to YouTube, tagging is one of the most important ways to rank your video in YouTube search results: Tags help users find your video when they search the site. When users type keywords related to your tags, your video will appear in their search results.”* Moreover, each thumbnail has been carefully selected to present the interviews and the content of each video as positive as possible.

Ending, in order to keep viewers interested and to keep them informed about the project’s activities, all videos are equipped with “end screens”, providing the users with the youtube channel subscription option and with a preview/promotion of the most relevant Families_Share interview.

The editing of the material took place with the use of Adobe Premiere Pro and with the EDIUS Pro 9, while pictures and video supers were developed via the use of Adobe Photoshop. Any additional logo, graphics and music inserted in all recordings are under the license of free Creative Commons License. All interviews were recorded in the national languages of each CityLab. The reasoning behind this choice was that interviewees would feel more comfortable

to share their experiences while it will be easier for the audience to understand but also to identify with them.

Ending, it needs to be mentioned that all the recordings were conducted under the knowledge of the recorded, no individual (parent-adult or child-minor) was filmed without having knowledge of the recording and without signing a relevant consent form. The consent form that was used is available in Section 6 - Appendix A.

6 Appendix A - Families_Share Consent form for Photography/Filming

Funded by the Horizon 2020
Framework Programme of the
European Union

Families_Share Consent form for Photography/Filming

Consent form for photography/filming

I consent to the Families_Share project and partners using photographs and/or video recordings including images of me both internally and externally to promote the Project and the project activities. These images could be used in print and digital media formats including print publications, websites, posters banners, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.

I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in the country I am located and that some overseas countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as EU legislation provides.

I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept online as archive of the Families_Share activities.

I have read and understand the conditions and consent to my images and to images of any minor, who I represent as the legal guardian, being used as described.

Name & Surname	
Signature	
Date	

The Families_Share Project along with its' partners is committed to processing information in accordance with the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**. The personal data collected on this form will be held securely and will only be used for administrative purposes.

Your rights
You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about you and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required. You can ask the Families_Share partners to stop using your images at any time, in which case it will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation. Please feel free to contacts us at any time!

Contact details
If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way, we are planning to use your information please contact:

Families_Share **Data Protection Officer, Coordinator and Dissemination WP Leader**, all available at the following dedicated mailing list:
info@families-share.eu |

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 CAPS Topic: ICT-11-2017, Type of action: IA, Grant agreement No 780783

7 Appendix B - Guidelines provided to partners prior to the audiovisual recordings.

1 File Instructions

This document is a set of instructions provided by WP5 leader -ViLabs in order to proceed with the needed video recordings during the pilot activities along with any other video recording activities, relevant to the Families_Share project. Please try to follow the provided instructions and please feel free to contact us Chatzimalis@vilabs.eu for any inquiries or suggestions.

A dedicated folder has been created under WP5 Dissemination and Sustainability Folder of the Families_Share Google Drive account, where you can find [a Families_Share consent form](#) to use before proceeding with any kind of recordings or photos. Moreover, you will find [an excel file for the subtitling activities](#), which will take place after the final edit of the audio-visual material.

At first, make sure that you have enough storage space on your mobile phone. Then, set the settings of the video resolution (1080 HD and 4K or whatever available).

Easy but essential, Clean your lens!

During the recording, please avoid zooming in digitally. Instead, “zoom with your feet” or simply walk closer to your subject, if you can.

2 Interviews

Samples of questions to ask:

- What’s your name and what group are you a part of?
- Why do you prefer this form of childcare?
- What are the most significant benefits for you?
- What are the most significant benefits for your children?
- What’s your favourite co-playing moment so far?
- Do you know what Families_Share is?
- Have you tried our Families_Share up?
- Do you think that our application could help you?
- Are you going to use our application?
- Would you suggest our application to others?

Ask them to say on the following= I support Families_Share, I embrace the community. Let’s become a Family.

3 Five Steps to make the Dissemination Manager Happy

- 3.1 Orientation:** Be sure to orient your phone horizontally. Portrait mode is a signal of an amateur video. Please avoid it.
- 3.2 Lighting:** Please avoid back lighting as much as possible. You should avoid having a window or light source behind your subject, since he or she will look silhouetted. Instead, you should have the light source more to the side of you or behind you.
- 3.3 Audio:** Thankfully, microphones on smartphones have improved a lot in the recent years. However, it is important to have a good audio of the speaking subject or generally. You can always use Bluetooth microphones which will maximise the quality of the audio, or you can try to have your mobile as close as possible to the speaker. Please, when interviewing subjects, do not interrupt their replies. In case, you understand that you do not have a clear audio recording you can either move your subject to a quieter corner or have a second phone recording only voice. Then, we can find out and connect voice and video! 😊
- 3.4 Steady - Use both hands:** You should always have both hands on the phone. It makes a big difference. The lenses of your phone have optical image stabilization built in, so they are already pretty stable. However, by using both hands, you will produce even steadier footage. At the same time, this will minimize the Jell-O effect - the wavy quality result you get when you move the camera too fast. With both hands you minimize the possibilities of such an effect. **Please make sure that your fingers are not part of the frame!**
- 3.5 Style:** The slower you move the better you record. Try to move the camera as slowly as possible, think of it as a photocopier. If you are moving the page the result will not be clear. Lock your focus. In low light, your phone's camera will hunt for focus. That makes it look less professional. Most phones let you also lock or manually adjust the exposure.
- 3.6 Quality:** Camera of 1920*1080 in terms of analysis. In case they pre-edit the footage, the export should be 1929*1080 h264 10mbps.

4 Storage

In order to save space and time, you can send the collected footage to chatzimalis@vilabs.eu via the <https://wetransfer.com/> application. Mpampis will collect them, storage them and contact the to the video and graphics designer.

5 Subtitling

After the final edit and review of the audio-visual material and right before publishing, (and in case this is needed) partners will have to provide the English translation for the subtitles of the interviews and videos in general. There is a dedicated excel file under the same folder.

